

UCC Bill and Women Status in Uttarakhand

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Received: 17/02/2024

1st BPR: 23/02/2024

2nd BPR : 28/02/2024

Accepted : 07/03/2024

Abstract

India is witnessing rapid modernization, urbanization, and social change. This dynamic has a profound impact on how various societies interact and evolve, leading to both integration and challenges. The vast disparity between urban and rural lifestyles, opportunities, and challenges significantly shapes the experiences of different societies within India. The concept of Uniform Civil Code entails the equal treatment of all sections of society, irrespective of their religious or caste affiliations. This progressive initiative, undertaken by the government of Uttarakhand, is poised to empower countless individuals by ensuring their rights are upheld. The implementation of a Uniform Civil Code will streamline legal frameworks across various faiths and tribes, unifying laws pertaining to critical matters such as marriage, divorce, inheritance, and maintenance. The UCC Bill is critical to create a truly empowering environment for women in Uttarakhand. Ultimately, the success of the bill lies not just in its provisions, but in its implementation in a way that respects diversity, empowers women in practice, and promotes true gender equality in the state.

Key words: UCC Bill, Uttarakhand, Women Status

Introduction

India is a land of immense diversity, and its vibrant social fabric is woven from countless threads representing various societies living together. Christianity, Sikhism, Hinduism, Islam, Buddhism, Zoroastrianism, and Jainism are major religions practiced in India, with numerous denominations and sects within each. This creates a rich tapestry of beliefs, customs, and traditions. India boasts over 22 official languages and countless dialects, representing various ethnicities and cultures. From the Dravidian south to the Indo-Aryan north, each region carries its unique linguistic and cultural heritage. Though officially abolished, the caste system continues to influence social hierarchy and relationships. Understanding its complexities and ongoing impact is crucial to fully comprehend Indian society. Adivasi or tribal communities, estimated at around 8.6% of the population, preserve distinct languages, customs, and governance systems, adding another layer to India's social diversity. The vast disparity between urban and rural lifestyles, opportunities, and challenges significantly shapes the experiences of different societies within India. India is witnessing rapid modernization, urbanization, and social change. This dynamic has a profound impact on how various societies interact and evolve, leading to both integration and challenges. Due to diverse religious, caste, tribal, rural-urban dynamics, as well as varying time frames, a multitude of regulations are observed by individuals across India. By this some irregularity happens from time to time when these types of rules are challenged to the Indian laws. So to control the conflicts there is a need for a new law like Uniform Civil Code.

Uttarakhand Population-

Uttarakhand boasts a multiethnic populace spanning two distinct geo-cultural regions: Garhwal and Kumaon. Approximately 35% of the population comprises Kshatriyas, encompassing diverse clans of former landowning rulers and their descendants. This demographic includes natives of Garhwal and Kumaon, as well as migrant communities.^{1, 2} As per a 2007 study conducted by the Centre for the Study of Developing Societies, Uttarakhand stands out with the highest proportion of Brahmins among all

states in India, accounting for approximately 20% of the population. Additionally, 18.3% of the population falls under the Other Backward Classes (OBCs) category.³ 18.76% of the populace comprises Scheduled Castes, denoting the lower castes within the traditional caste system in India, as per official terminology.⁴ Scheduled Tribes, including the Jaunsaris, Bhotiyas, Tharus, Buksas, Rajis, Jads, and Banrawats, make up 2.89% of the population. Additionally, various non-scheduled tribal groups, such as the Shaukas and Gurjars, inhabit the region. Notably, the Gurjars and Bhotiyas are nomadic tribes, while the Jaunsaris are a fully settled tribe.⁵

The Meaning of UCC-

This legislation, the Uniform Civil Code, mandates that all members of society receive equal treatment regardless of their religious or caste affiliations. It marks a significant stride initiated by the Uttarakhand government, poised to empower numerous individuals in securing their rights. By implementing a Uniform Civil Code, a unified legal framework will replace diverse customary laws across various faiths and tribes, addressing crucial matters such as marriage, divorce, inheritance, and maintenance uniformly.⁶

UCC Odyssey ⁷⁻

- In 1962, Jan Sangh talked about withdrawal of Hindu Marriage Act and Hindu Succession Bill. Jana Sangh then advocated for a uniform law for succession and adoption in 1967. The promise was repeated in 1971 also. However, there was no discussion on this issue in 1977 and 1980.
- BJP was formed in 1980. Atal Bihari Vajpayee became the first national president of BJP. The party contested elections for the first time in 1984, winning only two seats.
- 9th Lok Sabha elections were held in 1989, in which BJP included Ram Mandir, Uniform Civil Code in its election manifesto. The number of seats of the party increased to 85.
- In 1991, the 10th midterm elections were held in the country. This time BJP got more benefits. Its number of seats increased to beyond 100. In these Lok Sabha elections, BJP strongly raised the issues of Uniform Civil Code, Ram Temple, Section 370. All these issues were included in the election manifesto of BJP, but due to numerical strength they could not be completed.
- After this, in 1996, BJP formed the government for 13 days. In 1998, the party ran the government for 13 months. In 1999, BJP along with its allies formed the government with majority. Then Atal Bihari Vajpayee became the Prime Minister.
- For the first time in the year 2014, BJP came to power with a huge majority and the Modi government came to power at the centre. The Modi government started working on its election promises with full vigour. Now the Central Government is working towards implementing the Uniform Civil Code. In this context, Uttarakhand is moving towards becoming the first state in the country to implement UCC.
- In Uttarakhand, in 2022, BJP had kept the issue of UCC paramount and had promised that work would be done on it as soon as the government is formed. The Dhamsi government formed a committee for UCC. The special session of the Assembly is set to commence on February 5, marking a pivotal moment for Uttarakhand as it prepares to become the first state in the country to enact the Uniform Civil Code.

UCC Committee in Uttarakhand⁸⁻

The Government of Uttarakhand has established a Committee of Experts to assess the pertinent laws governing personal civil matters affecting the residents of Uttarakhand. The committee is tasked with drafting new laws or proposing amendments to existing ones concerning marriage, divorce, property rights, succession/inheritance, adoption, maintenance, custody, and guardianship. Additionally, the committee has been assigned the responsibility of preparing a report on the implementation of a Uniform Civil Code in Uttarakhand. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the issues at hand, the committee encourages residents of Uttarakhand and organizations based in the state, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations, social groups and communities, religious bodies, and political parties, to submit their opinions, views, suggestions, and representations within a 30-day period, concluding on or before October 7, 2022.

Hon'ble Committee Members:

Hon'ble Justice (Retd) Ranjana Prakash Desai	- Chairperson
Hon'ble Justice (Retd) Permod Kohli	- Member
Shri Shatrughna Singh, IAS (Retd)	- Member
Shri Manu Gaur, Social Activist	- Member
Prof. Surekha Dangwal, Vice Chancellor, Doon University	- Member
Shri Ajay Mishra, R.C., Uttarakhand	- Secretary

UCC in Uttarakhand⁹-

On February 7, 2024, the Uttarakhand Assembly made history by passing the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) Bill, marking the first instance in independent India where a legislature has enacted legislation proposing uniform regulations on marriage, divorce, inheritance of property, and live-in relationships for all citizens, regardless of their religious affiliations.

A Landscape of UCC Bill in Uttarakhand for Women -

The proposed Uniform Civil Code (UCC) Bill in Uttarakhand has ignited a complex debate, particularly regarding its potential impact on women's status in the state. While proponents hail it as a harbinger of gender equality, others raise concerns about unintended consequences and erosion of existing rights.

❖ Potential Positives:

- **Gender parity:** The bill promises equal inheritance rights for daughters and sons, addressing discriminatory practices prevalent in some personal laws. This empowers women financially and grants them greater agency within their families.
- **Combating polygamy:** The ban on polygamy could protect women from the harmful practice, safeguarding their well-being and preventing situations of emotional and economic hardship.
- **Standardized divorce procedures:** Uniform divorce grounds and procedures offer clarity and potentially streamline the process, making it less daunting and potentially more equitable for women seeking dissolution of marriage.
- **Registration of marriages:** Compulsory registration, if implemented effectively, could provide documented evidence of marriage, strengthening women's claims in situations of inheritance, maintenance, and legal disputes.

❖ Potential Concerns:

- **Overlooking specific needs:** One-size-fits-all approach might not address the diverse realities of women within different religious communities. Customary practices that offered some women certain protections could be lost.
- **Impact on inheritance in some communities:** While ensuring daughters' inheritance is positive, abolishing systems like Islamic inheritance law, where a daughter receives a smaller share, could disadvantage them in the short term, depending on family dynamics.
- **Limited empowerment:** The bill doesn't address crucial issues like domestic violence, workplace discrimination, and lack of access to education and healthcare, aspects critical for women's overall empowerment.
- **Practical challenges:** Effective implementation, particularly regarding registration of marriages and enforcement of provisions, is crucial to ensure the bill benefits women, especially in rural areas.

❖ Uncertainties and the Way Forward:

The final impact of the UCC Bill on women's status remains uncertain. Careful analysis of its nuances, considering specific community contexts and potential unintended consequences, is crucial. Engaging women's groups, legal experts, and community leaders in open dialogue is essential to ensure the bill truly upholds gender equality and does not inadvertently create new vulnerabilities.

Uttarakhand UCC Bill on marriage, divorce, guardianship, and adoption¹⁰

The Uttarakhand Uniform Civil Code (UCC) Bill of 2024 introduces notable amendments concerning marriage, adoption, and associated matters. Let's explore the alterations from the current framework.

Marriage registration is mandatory-

- Under the bill, it will be mandatory for every couple to register their divorce and marriage after March 26, 2010.
- Provision for registration at Gram Panchayat, Nagar Panchayat, Municipality, Municipal Corporation, Metropolitan Municipality level.
- Provision of maximum penalty of Rs 25 thousand for non-registration.
- Those who do not register will also be deprived of the benefits of government facilities.
- The minimum age for marriage has been fixed at 21 years for a boy and 18 years for a girl.
- Women can also make the same reasons and rights as the basis for divorce as men.
- Practices like Halala and Iddat have been abolished. There will be a ban on any kind of conditions for the woman to remarry.
- If someone changes religion without consent, then the other person will have the right to divorce that person and take maintenance allowance.
- It will be completely prohibited to marry again if a husband and wife are alive.
- In case of divorce or domestic dispute between husband and wife, the custody of the child up to five years of age will remain with the mother.

Equal Rights in Property¹¹⁻

- Son and daughter will have equal rights in property.
- There will be no difference between legitimate and illegitimate children.
- Illegitimate children will also be considered biological children of that couple.
- Adopted children born through assisted reproductive technology through surrogacy will be biological children.
- The property rights of the child growing in the womb of a woman will be protected.
- A person can give his property to any person by will.

Registration of Live in Relationship is Mandatory

Registration on the web portal will be mandatory for every person living in a live-in house.

- Couples will be able to take a house, hostel or PG on rent only after registration receipt.
- Children born in live-in will be considered legitimate children and will get all the rights of biological children.
- It will be mandatory for those living in live-in relationships to register their separation also.
- If mandatory registration is not done, there will be a provision of six months' imprisonment or a fine of Rs 25,000 or both.

No Law for Adoption-

- No law has been made for adoption in the Uniform Civil Code.

Marriage Laws and Divorce Laws-

These matters are regulated by the secular SMA-1954 (Special Marriage Act, 1954) as well as personal laws such as the HMA-1955 (Hindu Marriage Act of 1955), the ICMA-1872 (Indian Christian Marriages Act of 1872), the IDA-1869 (Indian Divorce Act of 1869), the PMDA-1936 (Parsi Marriage and Divorce Act of 1936), and both un-codified (Shariat) and codified Muslim Laws encompassing the Dissolution of MMA (Muslim Marriages Act.), the Protection of Rights on Marriage for Muslim Women (Act of 2019), and the Muslim Women - Protection of Rights on Divorce (Act of 1986).

Existing Laws on Parent-Child Relations-

Laws governing Parent - Child relations primarily revolve around Guardianship. While natural guardianship falls under PL (personal laws), Court appointed guardianship is addressed by the secular GWA -1890 (Guardians and Wards Act, 1890). Personal Laws regarding guardianship adhere to an outdated common law principle where the father assumes guardianship of the child, granting him the

authority to make decisions concerning the child and their assets. In contrast, the mother's role is typically confined to that of a caretaker, with limited decision-making powers. Additionally, children born out of wedlock are often considered "illegitimate" under personal laws, depriving them of certain entitlements, notably inheritance rights.

Although the SC (Supreme Court) has made efforts to rectify this bias by allowing the Mother to be appointed as guardian, in the situation if the father neglects his responsibilities and by granting inheritance rights in ancestral property to children born from void & voidable marriages, these advancements primarily apply within Hindu law. Regarding adoption, Hindus-Buddhists-Jains and Sikhs can adopt under the HAMA-1956 (Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956), while individuals of all religious backgrounds can adopt under the secular JJA-2015 (Juvenile Justice Act, 2015).

Registration of Marriages & UCC Bill-

The Bill mandates the registration of marriages and divorce decrees, retroactively applying these requirements. While there's no need for notice and objection during marriage registration, the Register of Marriages is accessible for public scrutiny after registration. This may disproportionately impact inter-caste and inter-religious couples, making them subject to surveillance. The aim here is to prevent bigamy and fraudulent marriages.

Under the Bill, unregistered marriages remain valid, but failing to registration of the marriage after a notice by the Sub Registrar incurs a fine of rupees twenty five thousand. This penalty mechanism encourages mandatory marriage registration. Non-registration of live-in relationships can result in imprisonment.

Marriages can be solemnized through any applicable ceremonies or rituals. Bigamy is prohibited across all communities, and customs imposing conditions on remarriage after divorce are criminalized. Non-prescribed modes of divorce, such as customary divorce deeds or panchayat divorces, are punishable. Divorce methods like talaq-us-sunnat, talaq-i-biddat, khula, maba'arat, and zihar all incur imprisonment. Additionally, Mehr and dower payments are recognized, supplementing any maintenance obligations specified in the Bill.

UCC-UK for Guardianship-

The Bill does not address the issue of guardianship, maintaining the dominance of personal laws in this regard. Similarly, court-appointed guardians will still be governed by the Guardians and Wards Act (GWA). Consequently, under the Bill, the father retains guardianship of the child, with the mother relegated to the role of custodian. The custody provision in the Bill reinforces this by stating that children up to the age of five will typically remain with the mother, without specifying if she also shares equal legal guardianship. The Law Commission's 2018 recommendation for equal parental rights to address discrimination against mothers is not reflected in the Bill.

On a positive note, the Bill ensures that children born from void and voidable marriages, as well as those from live-in relationships, will be considered legitimate and enjoy the same rights as children born within wedlock. However, children born from relationships falling below the defined threshold of a "nature of marriage" in live-in relationships may still be considered illegitimate.

UCC on Adoption-

The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act (HAMA) and the Juvenile Justice (JJ) Act will remain in force. Adoption under HAMA entails the transfer of the child from the surrendering parent or guardian to the adoptive parents. Calls for HAMA reform have emerged due to the absence of adoption registration or institutional oversight, raising concerns about potential misuse such as child trafficking. While the Uttarakhand Bill promotes compulsory registration of marriages and live-in relationships, it overlooks the necessity for adoption registration under Hindu law. This oversight represents a missed chance to overhaul Hindu adoption practices.

Some of the Concerns around Criminalisation-

The enforcement approach of the Bill hinges on criminalization, which could disproportionately affect minority communities. Various religious and customary practices of religious minorities have been

outlawed, potentially placing them at a disadvantage. Moreover, the surveillance mechanisms introduced by the Bill could be exploited to target and harass interfaith and inter-caste couples.

Conclusion:

Moreover, it is imperative to tackle broader issues such as economic opportunities, education, and social reforms in conjunction with the UCC Bill to foster a genuinely empowering environment for women in Uttarakhand. The effectiveness of the bill hinges not only on its provisions but also on its implementation in a manner that upholds diversity, empowers women in tangible ways, and fosters genuine gender equality across the state. The UCC holds significance in Uttarakhand for its role in advancing equality, curbing discrimination, ensuring equal rights for all residents, and fostering an environment of true equality.

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